

Multinuclear complexation equilibria of manganese(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) with L-2-amino-3-methylbutanoic acid (valine) and nitrilotriacetic acid

V. Shankar, G. K. Mishra and V. Krishna*

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : prof_vkrishna@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 10 March 2005, revised 28 December 2005, accepted 2 January 2006

Abstract : Equilibrium studies on mixed ligand-mixed metal complexes of manganese(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) with nitrilotriacetic acid and L-2-amino-3-methylbutanoic acid (valine) has been performed by potentiometric method. The stability constants of the complexes are determined in aqueous solution at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ ($I = 0.1 M \text{ NaNO}_3$). The calculations have been made using SCOGS computer program.

Keywords : Multinuclear complexes, stability constants, bivalent metal ions, valine, nitrilotriacetic acid.

Multinuclear complexes of transition metals are known to find application for understanding many reactions in living processes and many such complexes have been studied as model complexes¹. Considerable attention has also been paid in recent years² on the study of the mixed ligand/mixed metal complexes of aminopoly carboxylic acid with metal ions.

Results and discussion

The ligand NTA behaves as a tetradentate ligand, coordinating through a nitrogen and three carboxyl oxygen atoms. The secondary ligand valine functions as a bidentate ligand and coordinates through nitrogen and carboxyl group. Proton-ligand stability constants obtained for both the ligands are presented in Table 1, which are in good agreement with literature values³.

The formation of quaternary complexes in an aqueous solution may be conveniently expressed by the equilibrium :

The overall stability constant is given by :

$$\beta_{pqrst} = \frac{[M_p^1 M_q^2 A_r B_s (OH)_t]}{[M^1]^p [M^2]^q [A]^r [B]^s [OH]^t}$$

where the stoichiometric numbers p,q,r,s, are either zero or positive integer and t is a negative integer for a protonated species, positive for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species and zero for a neutral species.

Table 1. Formation constants of multimetal-multiligand complexes with nitrilotriacetic acid (A) and valine (B) in aqueous solution, at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ and $I = 0.1 M \text{ NaNO}_3$

(a) Proton-complexes formation constants log β of the ligands :				
NTA	AH ₃	AH ₂	AH	
log β	14.98	12.90	9.95	
Valine	-	BH ₂	BH	
log β	-	11.75	9.47	
(b) Hydrolytic constants (log β of metal-ions) :				
	Mn	Cu	Zn	Cd
M(OH) ⁺	-	-6.29	-7.89	-9.06
M(OH) ₂	-	-13.10	-14.92	-
(c) Stability constants (log β of binary complexes) :				
	Mn	Cu	Zn	Cd
MA	6.86	11.96	10.10	8.98
MB	2.82	8.71	4.61	6.96
(d) Stability constants (log β of ternary complexes) :				
	Mn	Cu	Zn	Cd
MAB	9.60	19.73	14.70	13.82
(e) Stability constants (log β of quaternary complexes) :				
	Cu-Mn	Cu-Zn	Cu-Cd	
M ¹ M ² AB	23.46	24.42	23.56	
Standard deviations are $\pm (0.1 - 0.2)$ in log unit.				

Only 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 (M¹ : M² : A : B) quaternary mixture have been used in this study to ensure the exclusive formation of the simplest M¹M²AB quaternary complex. Considering protonation constants of the ligands and hydrolytic constants of the M^{II} aqueous ions, the following species have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria.

AH₃, AH₂, AH, BH₂, BH, M(OH), M(OH)₂, MA, MB, MAB, M¹M²AB

Fig. 1. Distribution curves of Cu^{II} : Mn^{II} : NTA : valine 1 : 1 : 1 system : (1) AH₃, (2) AH₂, (3) AH, (4) BH₂, (5) BH, (6) Cu(OH)⁺, (7) CuA, (8) MnA, (9) CuB, (10) MnB, (11) CuAB, (12) MnAB, (13) Cu-MnAB.

Among the binary species, the concentrations of CuA and CuB complexes are found to be maximum at pH ≈ 5.0. Concentration of the binary complexes decreases with further increase in pH probably due to formation of ternary and quaternary complex species.

Fig. 2. Distribution curves of Cu^{II} : Zn^{II} : NTA : valine 1 : 1 : 1 system : (1) AH₃, (2) AH₂, (3) AH, (4) BH₂, (5) BH, (6) Cu(OH)⁺, (7) Zn(OH)⁺, (8) CuA, (9) ZnA, (10) CuB, (11) ZnB, (12) CuAB, (13) ZnAB, (14) Cu-ZnAB.

The distribution curves indicate the formation of ternary species in the pH range 4.0–8.0 according to equilibria :

The speciation curves also indicate the formation of heterobinuclear complex according to the following equilibria :

The stability constants, log β_{MA}^M, log β_{MB}^M, log β_{MAB}^M are presented in Table 1, and the speciation curves were obtained as computer outputs, log β_{MA}^M and log β_{MB}^M values are in good agreement with those reported in literature³. The speciation curves clearly show that the quaternary complexes attain their maximum concentration in the pH range 5.0–8.0, which suggests that quaternary complexation is favoured at low pH.

Fig. 3. Distribution curves of Cu^{II} : Cd^{II} : NTA : valine 1 : 1 : 1 system : (1) AH₃, (2) AH₂, (3) AH, (4) BH₂, (5) BH, (6) Cu(OH)⁺, (7) Cd(OH)⁺, (8) CuA, (9) CdA, (10) CuB, (11) CdB, (12) CuAB, (13) CdAB, (14) Cu-CdAB.

The overall stability constants β_{pqrst} of multinuclear complexes form a composite Irving-Williams⁴ order and this trend is found to be as :

Experimental

All the ligands used were of A.R. grade. A nitrilotriacetic acid (0.01 M) solution was prepared by dissolving it into two equivalents of alkali (NaOH) and metal solution was prepared and standardized as described earlier⁵. pH measurements were made with a century model Cp 901 pH-meter, using a special glass electrode (reproducibility ±0.01) pH. Equilibrium studies involved pH metric titration in aqueous medium keeping the concentration of common ingredients identical in all the cases. The ratio of Cu^{II} : M^{II} : NTA : valine was kept 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 (where M^{II} = Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}) and the total volume 50 ml. All the mixture solutions were titrated with carbonate free standard NaOH

solution at a fixed temperature 37 °C and ionic strength $I = 0.1 \text{ M NaNO}_3$.

Ionic product of water (K_w) at the experimental temperature and the activity coefficient of hydrogen ion at the experimental ionic strength were obtained from the literature⁶. Analytical concentrations of hydrogen ion corresponding to the pH meter reading were obtained by the usual procedure⁷. Formation constants (Table 1) were calculated with the add of the SCOGS computer program⁸. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the add of the species distribution curves (Figs. 1–3) obtained as computer out put.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (G.K.M.) would like to thank the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of research associate-ship.

References

1. D. R. Williams and C. C. Thomas, "An Introduction to Bioinorganic Chemistry", Illinois, 1976; H. Sigel, B. E. Fisher and E. Farkas, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 925; C. M. Perkins, N. J. Rose and R. E. Stenkamp, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **172**, 119; R. G. Bhirud and T. S. Srivastava, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **173**, 121; Q. Luo, C. Kong, Li Shen, S. Yu and Q. Lu, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1993, **18**, 583
2. G. N. Mukherjee, A. Das and S. Bandyopadhyay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 282; G. N. Mukherjee and H. K. Sahu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 209; Danuta Kroczevska, Barbara Kurzak and Ewa Matczak-Jon, *Polyhedron*, 2002, **21**, 2183; R. N. Patel, R. P. Srivastava, Nripendra Singh and K. B. Pandeya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 361; B. K. Srivastava, V. Shankar and V. Krishna, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 2005 (in press).
3. A. E. Martell and R. M. Smith, "Critical Stability Constants", Plenum Press, New York, 1974-1989, Vol 1-6.
4. H. M. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
5. G. K. Mishra, K. P. Singh and V. Krishna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 753.
6. E. M. Wolleym, D. G. Hurkot and L. G. Hepler, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 3908; H. S. Hamed and B. B. Owen, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", Reinhold, New York, 1958
7. H. M. Irving, M. G. Milles and L. D. Pettit, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1967, **38**, 475.
8. I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397; I. G. Sayce and V. S. Sharma, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 831